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THE IMPORTANCE OF PROFILING IN IDENTIFYING NARCOTIC DRUGS

ANNOTATION

The article characterizes profiling as a method of personality psychodiagnostics used to identify individuals who use the peculiarities of the intracavitary method of transporting drugs, and reveals some tactical techniques and features of profiling to identify drug couriers in passenger traffic.

Existing and actively used means of protection are focused mainly on the detection of narcotic drugs using, for example, technical means, sniffer dogs and security measures. However, these technologies do not allow identifying illegal intentions. Many years of successful experience in using the profiling method abroad, the positive results obtained also confirm the practical usefulness of this method in training law enforcement officers.

Key words: profiling, transportation, drugs, smuggling, movement, surveillance technology, passenger survey, control system, detection, warning.

GIYOHVANDLIK VOSITALARNI NOQONUNIY MUOMILASIGA QARSHI KURASHISHDA PROFAYLINGNI AHAMIYATI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada giyohvandlik vositalarni noqonuniy muomilasi bilan shug'ullanadigan shaxslarni aniqlashda profaylingdan foydalaniladigan shaxsiy psixodiagnostika usuli sifatida tavsiflanadi va narkokurerlarni aniqlashda inson parametrlarining profillashning ba'zi taktik usullari va xususiyatlarini ochib berilgan.

Mavjud va faol qo'llaniladigan texnik vositalar, xizmat itlari giyohvandlik vositalarni aniqlashga qaratilgan. Biroq, bu texnologiyalar inson niyatlarni aniqlashga imkon bermaydi. Rivojlangan xorijiy davlatlar profayling usulini qo'llash bo'yicha ko'p yillik muvaffaqiyatli tajriba, olingan ijobiy natijalar ham huquqni muhofaza qiluvchi organlar xodimlarini tayyorlashda ushbu usulning amaliy jihatdan foydali ekanligi tasdiqlanmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: profayling, tashish, giyohvandlik vositalar, kontrabanda, o'tkazish, kuzatuv texnologiyasi, yo'lovchilarni tekshirish, nazorat qilish tizimi, aniqlash, ogohlantirish.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ПРОФАЙЛИНГА ПРИ ВЫЯВЛЕНИИ НАРКОТИЧЕСКИХ СРЕДСТВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье дана характеристика профайлинга, как метода психодиагностики личности, применяемого для выявления лиц, использующих особенности внутриполостного способа перевозки наркотических средств, и раскрываются некоторые тактические приемы и особенности профайлинга по выявлению в пассажиропотоке наркокурьеров.

Существующие и активно используемые средства защиты ориентированы в основном на обнаружение наркотических средств с помощью, например, технических средств, служебных собак и режимных мероприятий. Однако при этом данные технологии не позволяют выявить противоправные намерения. Многолетний успешный опыт применения метода профайлинга за рубежом, полученные положительные результаты также подтверждают практическую полезность данного метода при подготовке сотрудников правоохранительных органов.

Ключевые слова: профайлинг, перевозка, наркотические средства, контрабанда, перемещения, технология наблюдения, опрос пассажиров, система контроля, выявления, предупреждения.

Today, existing and actively used means of protection are focused mainly on the detection of narcotic drugs using, for example, technical means, service dogs and security measures.

However, these technologies do not allow identifying illegal intentions. Accordingly, to resolve this issue, attempts are being made to create technologies that make it possible to identify illegal intentions by analyzing human psychophysiological reactions.

As an example, we can cite both the classic polygraph (lie detector) and such new developments: remote detectors of the psycho-emotional state of biological objects, vibraimage technology (“VibraImage”), the psychoprobing technique of Professor I. Smirnov - “Mine Reader”, “Silent Talker” (“Silent talker”), voice lie analyzers, bioradar method, etc. [1].

These technologies can be quite effective in detecting illegal intentions, but at the moment it is premature to talk about their widespread use to identify persons smuggling drugs.

The possibility of using such equipment is focused on the specifics of the functioning of transport infrastructure facilities, which may include: limited time allocated for checking passengers, the cost of such equipment, and the need to train personnel to work on it.

Today, only a person with a certain degree of probability is capable of reading internal information, determining the characteristics and dynamics of the behavior of other people, and promptly making appropriate decisions.

It seems that in this regard, the active introduction of profiling into the structure of transport security activities should bring tangible benefits in this area, since the method, which has proven itself with practical results, has the ability to qualitatively improve the entire range of measures to prevent the illegal transportation of narcotic drugs, of course, if the introduction of profiling is not simply a tribute to fashion or carried out formally.

Even the very training in profiling of security employees, as experience shows, has a positive effect on their subsequent attitude towards the performance of their immediate duties, since the approach to their immediate work changes in their minds.

Profiling forces you to more thoughtfully and carefully observe and analyze the entire environment, people’s behavior, look for suspicious signs and establish cause-and-effect relationships between various events, and take an unconventional approach to solving problems that arise in your work. These are very important skills for a person working in the security field [2].

Profiling (from the English “profile” - profile) is:

- a set of methods and techniques for assessing and predicting human behavior based on the analysis of the most informative signs, characteristics of appearance and behavior;
- technology for monitoring and interviewing passengers in order to identify potentially dangerous persons (at airports, railway, sea, river, bus stations, etc.).

Profiling technology began to be used in the late 70s of the twentieth century by the Israeli airline El Al. This technology was aimed at reducing the likelihood of possible risks associated with air transportation of passengers, and was used during pre-flight inspection.

As a rule, this was a set of questions that aimed to identify non-standard reactions of passengers to seemingly simple questions. This technology used a small set of basic psychological patterns (stereotypes of behavior) and was more reminiscent of a psychological testing procedure.

It should be noted that knowledge of the profiling method will allow police officers to conduct hidden “testing” of a potential attacker and build his “profile” to identify criminal intentions.

The profiling method will make it possible to make a fairly accurate assumption about the potential danger of a subject and can be used at bus stations, railway stations, airports and simply in crowded places for preventive measures both to prevent terrorism and to identify drug couriers.

Experience shows that profiling training has a positive effect on both the trainees and their subsequent attitude towards the performance of their immediate job responsibilities [3].

Profiling forces you to more thoughtfully observe and analyze the environment and people’s behavior, look for suspicious signs and establish cause-and-effect relationships, and take an unconventional approach to solving problems that arise in your work.

Thus:

- profiling is one of the ways to ensure security, as it allows you to prevent illegal actions by identifying potentially dangerous persons and situations;
- identification of potentially dangerous persons and situations is carried out using special technologies, which are based on a comprehensive analysis of such significant factors as: a person’s appearance and behavior, his transportation documents, luggage, things with him, etc.;
- profiling, as one of the methods for preventing illegal actions, can be used at all stages, places and activities to ensure aviation security and other protected/controlled objects and territories;
- within the framework of profiling, it is necessary to use psychological methods in their applied aspect, since special emphasis is placed here on the processes of interpersonal interaction, on the capabilities of human perception to read external and internal information, on the formation and development of such qualities as “observation”, “insight”, “communication skills”.

It should be noted that the organizers of the drug trade are constantly improving the ways and means of delivering drugs from the areas of their production to consumers. At the same time, they are trying to ensure their reliable protection and support, both from law enforcement agencies and from their competitors.

In this regard, one of the features of the drug business is the constant updating of the delivery system, the development of more and more thoughtful and unexpected routes, and the search for new methods of smuggling drugs.

As a rule, the so-called “disadvantaged” category of citizens who have low incomes or people who use drugs are recruited to transport drugs. The main task of the carrier (courier) is to transport the drug along the route specified to him.

He may not be aware of the person who is supposed to hand over the drug to him at the point of departure, or the person who is supposed to receive the “goods” at the point of arrival. At the same time, the courier knows exactly the nature of the cargo, the route and the “legend” of the trip.

Based on the analysis of statistics on the activities of the operational units of the Ministry of Internal Affairs in transport and operational customs units, drug traffickers use rail transport (90% of cases), air transport (5.5%) and road transport (4%) as the main mode of drug transportation.

Recently, the method of delivering small quantities of drugs by couriers has become widespread. In this case, narcotic substances are transported either in the luggage of a specific individual (usually in a hiding place), or on the body or in clothing, or with intracavitary concealment (i.e. in the body of the courier: stomach, intestines and other cavities that allow the drug to be extracted naturally without surgical or other intervention by unauthorized persons).

This method is especially actively used by Kazakh, Uzbek, Kyrgyz and Tajik groups. This method is used by organized criminal groups in conditions where it is necessary to quickly collect and deliver relatively small (usually up to 20 kilograms) batches of hard drugs and is used for passenger transportation on:

- railway transport;
- road transport;
- air transportation.

The safety of this method lies in the difficulty of detecting the data of drug couriers - swallows, and also in the fact that it is very difficult to detain all drug couriers, i.e. the loss of 1 or 2 drug couriers does not have a significant impact on the formation of a "custom" batch of drugs and entails minimal losses for organized criminal communities.

There is another type of drug smuggling carrier using intracavitary concealment - the so-called "Pushers". This type of carrier places the shipment of drug contraband into the rectal or vaginal cavity. For these purposes, cylindrical containers are used. Containers containing drugs are packaged in plastic materials and placed in one or two condoms.

To facilitate the process of placing containers into designated body cavities, drug smugglers use various lubricants such as petroleum jelly, moisturizers or hemorrhoidal creams.

According to foreign customs services, using the method of concealment described above, drug smuggling shipments can transport up to 500 g of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances.

Containers for concealing drug smuggling are, as already mentioned, cylindrical in shape with average dimensions from 5 to 10 cm in length and from 2 to 4 cm in thickness, into which it is possible to store from 50 to 100 g of drugs.

The dimensions above may vary significantly depending on the individual carrier. For example, female couriers most often use package-shaped containers from 10 to 13 cm long and an average width of 3.8 cm. [4].

Transportation of drug smuggling using the intracavitary method of concealment provides a relatively low probability of detection, but at the same time it is a complex and dangerous method of transportation for the life and health of the carrier.

In addition, intracavitary concealment methods have limited capabilities in terms of the volume of contraband transported. For these reasons, the use of such concealment methods is used to deliver the most expensive types of drugs, which are currently heroin and cocaine.

In this regard, the concept of profiling is precisely based on building a passenger profile. The main methodological point is that persons who have transported drugs are characterized by the presence of a certain set of suspicious signs in their appearance, behavior, travel documents and transported items.

The study and systematization of these signs makes it possible to create a passenger profile, on the basis of which each person can be classified as non-dangerous or potentially dangerous. In accordance with this, all passenger traffic is processed according to a certain scheme, which makes it possible to identify suspicious signs.

Work with a passenger can begin with collecting preliminary information about him using various databases. Then, according to current practice, before checking in for a flight, the passenger's travel documents are examined, all the things he is carrying are inspected, and the general appearance and behavior of the person and those accompanying him are analyzed. Particular attention is paid to studying documents in order to detect signs of forgery.

The most convenient place for profiling during pre-flight inspection is the area in front of the check-in counters, where the passenger is with all the things he is carrying. The work of the profiler can be carried out at the position of the first number of the screening officer or next to him.

In profiling, a special baggage control survey system has been developed, which allows us to identify the possible presence of dangerous or prohibited items for transportation carried by a passenger or transferred to him by other people.

Emphasizing to the passenger that the survey is being conducted for his safety creates a positive attitude toward contact with the profiler. In this process, the profiler's intuition and professional experience are of great practical importance. Standard questions, depending on the situation, may concern the purpose of the trip, purpose and place of stay, cultural and historical monuments, etc.

In the profiling system, the peculiarities of behavioral reactions of the passenger and those accompanying him are of great interest. Accordingly, it is advisable for the profiler to have some specialized knowledge in the field of applied psychology.

Identification of suspicious aspects in the appearance and behavior of people is possible through the use of psychological testing in the work of a profiler, which is understood here as a visual diagnosis of a person's internal state through visible manifestations of characteristic signs, possibly indicating an impending illegal act.

In this case, we are talking about professional observation of a person according to a certain scheme. For employees of the Ministry of Internal Affairs in transport, it is very difficult to identify those persons who are transporting drugs using intracavitary concealment.

Organizers of drug smuggling use this complex and risky method for the health of the carrier, since it is very difficult to detect during customs control, and in case of failure, the police officer, customs or SAB is subject to justified complaints and claims from the passenger.

At the same time, drug smuggling couriers develop and use special techniques and methods in order to make the very fact of transportation as secretive and outwardly invisible as possible. However, as practice shows, in order to detect such couriers, experience, knowledge and attention to risk factors and signs of possible drug trafficking are required.

Detection of drugs transported intracavitarily includes the following steps:

- identification among passengers of persons who, based on a combination of signs, may be involved in the transportation of drugs in this manner;
- carrying out actions and measures to verify suspicions that have arisen;
- detention of persons in respect of whom suspicions are justified, and their medical examination;
- seizure of drugs discovered during the examination, documentation of the fact of their intracavitary transportation and seizure.

Screening of passengers should be carried out primarily on routes and flights that originate from regions known to be sources or suppliers of drugs. The passenger's expected level of income, his social status, occupation, appearance and cost of luggage, ticket, and the correspondence of these characteristics to the purposes of the trip are subject to analysis.

You should pay attention to persons traveling without luggage, with small luggage or with camouflaged luggage. The lack of luggage is due to the fact that muscle tension when moving it can provoke the release of containers for both "swallowers" and "pushers".

The technique of camouflaging luggage is used by couriers so as not to stand out from the general mass of typical passengers on a given route. To do this, they carry large bags or trunks, typical of "shuttle traders" or vacationers, but filled with light, bulky things.

A discrepancy between the weight and volume of baggage can be detected during weighing during check-in (in air transport; recently scales have also been installed at large railway junctions to control the weight of cargo carried by passengers), as well as during visual inspection, when it is clear that the baggage is large the passenger moves without visible effort.

The desire to prevent tension in the muscles of the abdominal cavity and perineum leading to the exit of containers is related to the peculiarities of the movement of passengers who are couriers-swallowers. The carrier tries to strain these muscle groups as little as possible, and therefore his movements are most often inhibited, slow, tense and limited [5].

This is expressed in the way the passenger moves and the peculiarities of his gait: the passenger moves very tensely, in short steps, slowly, without sudden movements. When moving luggage, he tries to do it slowly (lift, lower).

Peculiarities are also manifested in the way of sitting: they tend to bend one leg under themselves or transfer the body weight to one side, while holding the support with the other hand in order to relieve tension in the abdominal muscles. A distinctive feature is also the method of placing the intracavity on a hard surface: first on one buttock, and then on the other.

It should be noted that the intracavity method of concealment greatly complicates the detection of illegal drug trafficking. Firstly, this is due to the difficulties of identifying this method of transportation, since many traditional methods and means are ineffective - the usual inspection of cargo, luggage and personal belongings of passengers, including the use of technical means and sniffer dogs.

Suppressing the illegal transportation of drugs intracavity involves the use of additional and specific techniques and methods for identifying intracavity drug couriers, examining them and documenting facts of illegal transportation.

Secondly, in case of failure, the actions of internal affairs and customs officials can be reasonably appealed by citizens.

Therefore, identifying and detaining drug smuggling transported using intracavity concealment is very difficult and requires employees of inspection services (customs, transport police) to have the appropriate knowledge, experience and professional skills.

The current situation related to ensuring aviation security in general and the suppression of drug trafficking in particular, involves the development of various practical measures and basic legal provisions for the use of profiling in security systems in all sectors of the country's transport complex.

The creation of an appropriate methodological and legislative framework for the use of profiling will enable security services (police) to successfully use this method of identifying a potential offender.

The most promising areas in which profiling technology can be used are the following:

- use of profiling technology as part of pre-flight inspection;
- use of profiling methods such as observation, questioning, manual baggage inspection and personal (individual) search;
- use of profiling by employees of the Security Service and internal affairs bodies in their activities;
- introduction of profiling technology or its elements to ensure the safety of the aircraft during post-flight inspection of passengers.

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